

Understanding Animal Consciousness: To test awareness

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A belief amongst the common population is the thought that Homo sapiens have achieved a higher level of consciousness, alongside a heightened sense of intellectuality. As we have examined surrounding species our ideas have only been supported, sure we acknowledge an individual species smartness but dare we not compare it to ours. Society has shunned such an act out of existence.

However this matter is something that cannot be set aside. Do animals possess a similar sense of awareness to ours? The question of if the minds of species around us could be of a similar nature to ours, is one heavily tested upon and experiencing major view changes as science progresses, contrasted by heavy controversy.

First we shall begin to come to a general consensus about the concept of animal consciousness. Consciousness refers to the overall state of being aware, but the deeper and more advanced definition of what it means to be alive or conscious is not agreed on, "there may [even] be "alien" forms of consciousness which do not manifest in the ways typical for human consciousness"(Dung), which makes it puzzling to understand what may point towards consciousness in other species

Nevertheless we know that animal awareness can be a visible action that indicates a species intelligence. The individual's awareness can be shown through their reaction to different stimuli. A famed test performed on a multitude of species is the 'mirror test'. The purpose is to see if they are able to recognize themselves in the mirror which could hint to awareness. There are many more experiments done in a comparable way. However many of these tests are, in a way, biased.

These tests are made in a way to measure the human definition of intelligence making them biased. Over decades our perception and understanding of other species has changed, we have come to the understanding that one notion may be displayed differently in another species to be more effective. Intelligence is truly shown through the efficiency of acts performed by a species that are necessary for survival; to be smart is to be able to perform the tasks that are essential for that species survival.

Different tasks may be more efficient to our species compared to another, testing them on what is significant to us is simply unjustified. This is the case as if we set what is necessary for ourselves as the example we become narcissistic and ignorant. This blockade of the want for knowledge can lead to no further development, for the lack of curiosity and care produces no positive influence in understanding an animal's consciousness and intellectuality.

The fact different behaviours can be more or less efficient means behaviour cannot always be used to measure an individual's level of intellectuality. If doing so, one would have to take much consideration on which actions are needed. But, it does prove whether or not an individual possesses a conscience. A way to observe if one is sentient, is to identify vital senses such as "[t]he most primitive type of self-awareness ... [,] *bodily self-awareness*, an awareness of one's own body as importantly different from the rest of the environment"(DeGrazia) . The mental differentiation of the body and its surroundings is shown by the individual's actions "as [it is] directly connected with certain feelings and subject to one's direct control. Because of bodily

self-awareness, one does not eat oneself”(DeGrazia). The site even goes on to “suggest that most or all sentient animals have this type of self-awareness.”

Humanity's form of consciousness is not nearly the most advanced. There are forms of consciousness that we could not even conjure, there are things we don't even know to look for, even the forms of awareness we do possess knowledge of are still being studied. But, as we find more we widen our perspective to other kinds of awareness we learn that setting ours as the example is fully ignorant, as we find variant awareness types that are exuded in a way we would never be able to experience ourselves. Some we may coincide with is the development of language but an example that is seen in many species is magnetoreception. Magnetoreception is a vital part of survival to those who possess this trait/ability.

A topic within the discussion of miscellaneous awareness forms is the way cephalopods experience it. Cephalopods have been a heavily questioned group, shrouded in mystery and acted as a source of curiosity for many years. Many theories surround them in scale from if they dream to if they're literally aliens.

When mirror tests were done to indicate octopus self-awareness the results were unpromising as “[e]vidence for mirror self-recognition in cephalopods is weak. Several species of octopus ... show no response when presented with a mirror”. On the other hand “[o]ther cephalopod species ... display interest toward their reflection but respond with agonistic behaviors”(Schnell et al.) . Even though this method is a highly favoured one still used today (specifically for testing self awareness) it does not fully determine if the species is self-aware for “they are unlikely to encounter an object in their environment that has the properties of a mirror”. Meanwhile this evidence alone does not give enough evidence to state if they are self-aware we do have appropriate reason to believe that they do. “The lack of a rigid structure allows them to adapt the shape of their body to their environment. They can squeeze into small spaces, change the length of their arms, bend their arms in all directions, and use them to manipulate objects with exceptional dexterity The ability to fluidly change posture and overall body size suggests that cephalopods can recognize, and act upon, the distinction between oneself and their physical environment”(Schnell et al.) . It is saddening to see such a vastly used method fail, it works great for mammals, however when dealing with such different groups it just isn't suitable for their lifestyle and the way they think.

In conclusion, consciousness is an intricate notion done in many ways. The basic belief that being able to complete difficult tasks for a human is considered smart is grossly oversimplified. In reality those abilities necessary for a human are properties of intelligence and consciousness for a human, not for other species. Other species have different motivations; they will perform different tasks using different types of awareness such as electroreception or extraocular vision. Consciousness is shown by different types of awareness consisting of different types of tasks. To be intelligent is to be able to perform the tasks needed to survive.

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